

Evaluation of Vocational Training during the COVID-19 Pandemic Period in Indonesia

Stevanus Agung Wibowo¹, Tomi Setiawan², Sinta Ningrum³

^{1,2,3} Padjadjaran University, Bandung, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT: Research based on the conditions of the COVID -19 pandemic and government policies in reducing unemployment through vocational training. However, the vocational training program at the Ministry of Manpower during the COVID -19 pandemic period in 2021 did not have a significant impact. This study aims to evaluate the ministry of workforce's vocational training program during the COVID -19 pandemic in 2021. The research was conducted through a qualitative approach using the CIPP guidance theory. Data collection methods using observation and unstructured and semi-structured interviews, documents, and literature studies. The research uses data analysis techniques with three stages, in the form of data condensation, data presentation, and conclusion and verification. The results of the study concluded that the vocational training program at the Ministry of Manpower had not been successful in terms of input, process, and product aspects. From the input aspect, the vocational training program's resources are insufficient. From the process aspect, there are still constraints on the realization of the training, supervision, and instructor skills. Meanwhile, from the product aspect, it cannot be ensured that the participants will be placed after training.

KEYWORDS: CIPP, Evaluation, Program evaluation, VET, Vocational training.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 has become a great pandemic throughout the world, including in Indonesia. To overcome the pandemic, the Indonesian government issued Government Regulation 21 of 2020 concerning large-scale social restrictions to accelerate the handling of the 2019 coronavirus disease. Large-scale social conditions ((abbreviated as *PSBB*), are one of the government's strategies in dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic. However, its implementation is still limited to controlling its spread, focusing on public health (Saputra & Salma, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has had a broad impact on the Indonesian economy. One of the impacts affected is the employment sector. So intervention by the Indonesian government is needed at the central and regional levels during the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic also presents challenges for employment and digitalization in Indonesia.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, digitalization has become increasingly visible in the workforce—digitization supported by dynamic employment conditions, flexible working relationships, and digital automation 4.0. Industrial revolution 4.0 rests on the more thoughtful use of digital technology. So digitalization is transforming the employment sector, especially the workforce's quality, to adapt to the dynamic conditions of the job market. From the point of view of public administration, employment policy can be used as a direction to determine strategy in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0. The plan for achieving the employment policy goals in Indonesia during the digitalized industrial revolution 4.0 is to create a vocational training program.

The achievement of vocational training performance in 2021 had a target of 65% and was realized at 59.12%. Detailed achievements are as follows, first, Competency-based training, a target of 120,046 people, with training realization of 122,119 people and realization of placement of 35,999 people. Second, the target of domestic apprenticeship was 108,300, and the training of 21,262 people was realized—the realization of the placement of 11,916 people. Third, overseas Apprentices have a target of 600, with actual training of 583 people. Realization of placement of 583 people. Four, the independent workforce has a target of 100,000 people, and the realization of training is 89,536 people. Realization of the placement of 89,536 people. Based on the data above, the results of the Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development explained that the indicators had yet to reach the planned targets. The target that still needs to be achieved is the actual placement. So the planned program requires evaluation. Evaluation is a systematic process of describing, obtaining, reporting, and applying descriptive information and judgments about several benefits, values, fairness, feasibility, safety, significance, and equity (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014). Evaluation means a process that has been structured to find out information about the implementation of a policy. This process involves various parties, consisting of individuals, groups, and communities, that provide impact certainty to beneficiaries.

Based on the data above, the results of the Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development explained that the indicators had yet to reach the planned targets. The target that still needs to be achieved is the actual placement. So the planned program requires evaluation. Evaluation is a systematic process of describing, obtaining, reporting, and applying descriptive information and judgments about several benefits, values, fairness, feasibility, safety, significance, and equity (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014). Evaluation means a process that has been structured to find out information about the implementation of a policy. This process involves various parties, consisting of individuals, groups, and communities, that provide impact certainty to beneficiaries. In the 2020 performance report, the indicator for the Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development s has a target of 126,718 people working to achieve performance indicators. Still, the realization produced was 44,754 people, achieving 35.31%. With it, Law number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation provides fresh air for the economic investment sector during this pandemic. In this regard, preparations for increasing the competence of the workforce are needed to meet the link and match the needs of the labor market. On the contrary, based on data from the Ministry of Manpower information data center, during the industrial revolution 4.0. there are still many skilled workers: “Semi-skilled 89.6 million, skilled 13.7 million, basic skilled 24.5 million. The basic skills in question are in the form of a class of unskilled workers. Semi-skilled workers include administrative staff, service business personnel, sales personnel, agricultural, forestry, skilled fishery workers, craft processing workers, and machine operators and assemblers. Skilled consists of managers, professionals, technicians, and assistants.” (Information data center Manpower of Republic Indonesia, 2021).

This can be interpreted as the importance of evaluation in managing programs included in the work plan. Therefore, apart from paying attention to the structure of the vocational training program through written regulations, the vocational training program requires the involvement of an evaluation of the implementation that has occurred so that the program stated in the plan can achieve its target. This phenomenon is related to the facts that occur related to the vocational training program. The authors found indications of problems with vocational training; First, the implemented program still needs help with employment absorption in the job market, with an indicator below 50%. This can be seen in the performance of 1 Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development in 2020 that there are still as many as 81,964 people who have yet to be absorbed by the job market. Second, Indonesian HR Skills to meet the link and match in the job market will take much work to achieve, considering that the proper job market requires human resources ready to work. This is supported by data from the Ministry of Manpower information data center during the industrial revolution 4.0. There are still many workers, semi-skilled 89.6 million, skilled 13.7 million, and basic skilled 24.5 million. Third, Indonesian Workers will be faced with competition from Foreign Workers who already have sufficient skills, and Indonesian Workers will find it increasingly difficult to compete in the job market. According to the information data center of the Ministry of Manpower for foreign workers working in Indonesia, as of August 2020, there were 93,761 people.

Therefore, In this study, we believe that it is essential to see and explore and evaluate the ministry of manpower's vocational training program during the COVID-19 pandemic period (2021) to know the performance of the vocational training program. Based on the description above, this study aims to provide recommendations for the lack of performance of the vocational training program.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative method. Creswell (2013) argues that qualitative research should be conducted to understand as deeply as possible so that the knowledge structure from the researcher can be transmitted to the participants, spend more time researching, deepening information, and message to get detailed information. To uncover new information and understand the complexities of meaning in the evaluation of vocational training programs, this study used in-depth interviews conducted in an open and semi-structured manner. Data collection was also done through observation and document review. The fieldwork was conducted for five months from January to July 2022.

Interviews were conducted with several key informants, consisting of the functional planner, budgeting program sub-coordinator, vocational training organizing sub-coordinator, reporting evaluation sub-choir, instructor training development analyst, the expert level planner I, program evaluation reporting secretariat, north Jakarta regional job training center instructor, vocational training participants. Through observation, the researcher can cross-check or supplement data and information obtained from in-depth interviews conducted or study documents and archives to get more information and a detailed description of field conditions. Document studies are carried out by searching, collecting, mapping, processing, and analyzing secondary data, including 1) strategic

plans/performance reports 2) legal documents, and 3) other relevant documents, such as articles/manuscript reports related to the research.

The collected data is then analyzed. The analysis results provide a basis for researchers to interpret the data to gain insight into the underlying meaning of various social processes and interactions that reflect reality on the ground. In addition, the processing and analysis of field data are done by organizing and arranging the data. In research, the authors use data analysis techniques (Miles & Huberman, 2014), namely, condensation data, display data, conclusion drawing, and verification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Context (Context Evaluation).

In the regulation of the Ministry of Manpower number 10 of 2021, The Ministry of Manpower has designed a strategic plan that is supportive based on the vision and mission of the President-Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia for 2020-2024 and aims to create a workforce that is competent, tough, agile and competitive in industrial relations conducive. Further strengthened by Presidential Regulation Number 18 of 2020 concerning the 2020-2024 National Medium-Term Development Plan, then Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System, and Decree of the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development Number 2/2887/LP.03.02 /XII/2021 Concerning Technical Guidelines for Organizing Competency-Based Training for the 2022 Fiscal Year.

Following the dynamics that occur with the times, the strategic plan of the Ministry of Manpower directs employment development policies on the issue of increasing productivity and the quality of the workforce. This policy direction can be interpreted as increasing human resources as a priority for the Ministry of Manpower.

Based on the problems and policy direction, the Ministry of Manpower initiated vocational training to improve the quality of human resources in Indonesia. This policy aims to create a healthy, intelligent, adaptive, innovative, and skilled workforce through increased productivity. Based on these goals, the expected goal is in the form of Employment Link and Match, namely the suitability of the skills of the individuals trained with the demands of the labor market.

The agenda that the Ministry of Manpower focuses on is developing a system of training, certification, and placement to digitize labor market services. Based on Ministry of Manpower regulation number 10 of 2021, the need for the target objective of the vocational training program is to reduce unemployment. The program has a target indicator of a slight yearly increase through the Ministry of Manpower's strategic plan for 2021-2024. The target of increasing competence is only 65%, 68%, 72%, and 75%. This means that it only increases by 3-5% every year. So in responding to the needs of the future labor market conditions through vocational training programs, it still needs to answer the needs appropriately.

Based on the interview results of the author, there is Presidential Regulation Number 68 of 2022 concerning the Revitalization of Vocational Education and Vocational Training. In this case, Vocational Training is a duty and responsibility carried out by the Ministry of Manpower. Based on the regulations above, it intends to answer the needs of the business world, the industrial world, the world of work, and entrepreneurship. So that the vocational training policy in implementation still needs to be appropriate to answer the problems of employment conditions in achieving the goals of vocational training. In this connection, in the context aspect, interpreting needs, problems, assets, opportunities, and conditions from contextual dynamics related to the Ministry of Manpower's regulatory policy number 10 of 2021, is not yet suitable to answer all the labor dynamics that exist in Indonesia to bring together supply and demand. Demand or link and match from the condition of the labor market in Indonesia.

In this dimension, the researcher analyzes that the Ministry of Manpower requires several needs. First, with dynamic employment conditions, flexible working relationships, and digital automation 4.0. This means that the need for context evaluation comes from the environment within the scope of the Ministry of Manpower. This can undoubtedly be seen from the existing job market conditions, with the shift in job demand from initially conventional to automation or the ability to use technology. Second, the presence of Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation Indonesian presidential regulation Number 68 of 2022. Along with the Job Creation Law and the Revitalization of Vocational Education and Vocational Training, this policy can increase the market. So, with the existence of regulations supporting the ease of investing and doing business in Indonesia coupled with the focus of the Indonesian presidential regulation, which aims to increase competent and competitive Indonesian human resources.

Opportunities from the Job Creation Law and Indonesian presidential regulation number. 68 of 2022 makes it a breath of fresh air for investors to invest so that it can simultaneously encourage increased investment in Indonesia. Further developments in digital

technology create new jobs and skills that are useful for increasing entrepreneurial opportunities, increasing the flexibility of the labor market, and facilitating information in the labor market. Until now, the term digital nomad has been written as follows: "The term "digital nomad" describes people who no longer rely on work in a conventional office; instead, they can decide when and where to work." (Müller, 2016).

In the future, a person will be free to determine for themselves, work anywhere and anytime, and not depend on conventional offices. Of course, this is easy to do as long as they are connected to an affordable laptop and internet. The Ministry of Manpower's strategic plan explains that the ease of access to digital technology can raise market demand for the abilities of individual workers. Therefore, the government's adaptation in responding to and taking advantage of the opportunities and challenges that occur in the future is very high due to the uncertainty of the desires and needs of the labor market.

The needs of the changing labor market and the need for individuals to adapt to the global market requirements are considered reasons for the practice of digital nomads. Digital Nomad during the industrial revolution 4.0 is increasingly felt, occurring in everyday life with uncertain and flexible jobs, as explained in the article: "Digital nomadism is driven by important societal changes, such as the ubiquity of mobility and technology in everyday lives and increasingly flexible and precarious employment." (Olgas, 2020).

Based on the type of shift above, skills are also a separate demand for the individual workforce in dealing with the required preparation. Referring to the Regulation of the Minister of Manpower Number 10 of 2021, there are 15 skills needed until 2025, as shown; analytical and innovative thinking, active learning and learning strategies, complex problem solving, critical thinking and analysis, creativity, originality and initiative, leadership and social influence, use of technology, monitoring, and control, technology design and programming, resilience, stress tolerance and flexibility, reasoning, problem-solving and ideation, emotional intelligence, troubleshooting, and user experience, service-oriented, system analysis, and evaluation, persuasive and negotiating.

Based on interviews with employees of the Performance Planning and Management Bureau, there has been a change in requests for digital job shifts. Through this statement, there is a dynamic condition in the labor market, which demands new types of jobs caused by technological developments and the digital economy. This is what is referred to as a problem in labor conditions in Indonesia along with the digital revolution 4.0. Looking at the conditions and dynamics of the job market, the working relationship has changed, such as the emergence of part-time, freelancing, etc. This kind of working relationship is the designation of the GIG Economy, which is explained below: "We use the term 'gig economy' to refer to labor markets that are characterized by independent contracting that happens through, via, and on digital platforms. The kind of work that is offered is contingent: casual and non-permanent work. It may have variable hours and little job security, involve payment on a piece-work basis, and lack any options for career development. This relationship is sometimes termed 'independent contracting', 'freelancing' or 'temporary work' ('temp' for short)." (Woodcock & Graham, 2020).

The author can conclude that in terms of evaluating vocational training, it has been able to answer all the needs required by the Ministry of Manpower. The context aspect is from the legal basis, perpendicular to the president's directives to the latest presidential regulation number 68 of 2022. Then, look at the problem of the dynamic conditions of the volatile job market and unemployment from the impact of the pandemic. Furthermore, looking at opportunities for legal product support from work copyrights, Indonesia's demographic conditions, and the development of the industrial revolution 4.0. So to answer the need for vocational training, it is appropriate in terms of context.

Input (Input Evaluation).

Based on the results of interviews with the functional planners of the Bureau of Planning and Performance Management, vocational training receives a budget from the Ministry of Finance and funds from the education function. However, he explained that the trend of granting the budget fluctuated every year. as in the following figure:

Figure 1. Vocational Training Budget
Source: Research finding, 2022

Based on the graphs and statements from the Functional Planning Bureau of Planning and Performance Management, the budget provided by the Ministry of Finance for implementing the vocational training program fluctuated. It can be seen that the budget in 2019 increased, but in the following year until 2021, it decreased, and in 2022 it increased again. According to the author, this is reasonable because considering the COVID-19 pandemic and the government's focus, according to Minister of Finance Regulation 17 of 2021, to prioritize public health by refocusing on the health sector.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the budget has been refocused four times in the form of budget cuts. Furthermore, in implementing the vocational training program, the Ministry of Manpower also has other programs and stated that the budget provided was not in proportion to the budget required for its implementation.

By the planning function, the Sub-Coordinator of Budgeting, the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development, stated that there were limited budgets. He explained that this was due to post-recovery economic conditions. This can be seen by looking at the performance report of the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development for 2021, the initial budget ceiling for 2021 was 3,992,500,410,000, and the budget was refocused, becoming 2,485,438,547,000. In the author's opinion, the budget for implementing the vocational training program is still inadequate to achieve the target from the initial planning. According to the author, this is a problem because considering the COVID-19 pandemic and the government's focus on prioritizing public health by refocusing the budget on the health sector.

There are three types of Vocational and Productivity Training Centers. Vocational and Productivity Training Center, Class I Vocational and Productivity Training Center, and Class II Vocational and Productivity Training Center. 21 Central Technical Implementation Units owned by the Ministry of Manpower are spread across 15 Provinces in Indonesia. Through this, there is still a need for training centers spread evenly in each province, which can interfere with improving the quality of human resources nationally, given the massive and dynamic industrial development. Based on interviews with various informants, the facilities and infrastructure for implementing the vocational training program are inadequate. The following writings also support the results of the interviews: "The available facilities and infrastructure are computers in damaged condition, but repairs have not been carried out due to limited operational costs. Apart from that, the availability of parking space is less extensive, so vehicles are less organized, and the need to add or repair toilets because there is only one." (Ernawati & Suyantiningsih, 2020).

Based on the research Fadilah and Rosdiana explained, there are still inadequate facilities in terms of quantity and quality. This is supported as follows: "It can be seen that the training practice room is very narrow and the equipment owned by industrial electricians is inadequate both in terms of quantity and quality. Most of the equipment was damaged or scratched during use, then the number of equipment was inadequate, so participants had to take turns if they wanted to use it." (Fadilah & Rosdiana, 2015).

Based on the statement above, the vocational training program's budget, facilities, and infrastructure still need to be fulfilled in its implementation. Experiencing problems with facilities and infrastructure, of course, can impact the objectives of the vocational training program. Therefore, it can impact training instructors, training participants, and achievement targets from the Ministry of Manpower.

According to the Functional Planning of the Ministry of Manpower, human resources in implementing vocational training programs are instructors. The instructor referred to in this case is a civil servant, owned by the Ministry of Manpower in the ability to transfer knowledge to trainees. Then, the instructor also acts as the front person who conducts coaching to prospective trainees. Furthermore, in the Decree of the Director General of Vocational Training Development and Productivity Number 2/2887/LP.03.02/XII/2021, the duties and roles of the instructor are written, namely in the form of assisting, guiding, and observing vocational training participants. In line with Setiyaningrum's findings, "Instructors have an important role in the smoothness and success of an education and training program." (Setiyaningrum, 2016).

An instructor certainly has specific requirements needed to prepare professional instructors. So that the training participants can easily absorb the delivery of vocational training materials. The conditions that apply in the regulation of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration No. 8 of 2014 are in the form: First, have methodological competence and technical competence. Second, obtain an assignment from the Head of the Training Institute through an assignment letter. Third, it can consist of instructors, experts, or equivalent terms.

Furthermore, one of the instructor's ability requirements is in the form of presentation of material, as well as systematic material components and games; this is described as follows, "Instructor's ability to provide competent training and supported by a certificate as an instructor. In addition, the systematic presentation of material and material components makes it easier for trainees to receive the material, feel comfortable, and provide games in between giving material so that the learning atmosphere is not monotonous." (Ridwan & Suryono, 2015).

This ability has a good role for the trainees. With the vocational training, the participants hope that the material will be easy to absorb and valuable for work in the future. This is supported in the writings of Ridwan and Suryono as follows: "Trainee participants who take part in vocational training understand the material provided, and there are three aspects that the participants get in the learning process, namely: the participant's attitude is well formed, the participant understands the vocational training material, and the participant can develop the skills acquired during the learning process." (Ridwan & Suryono, 2015).

However, the ability of human resources in its implementation is still considered inadequate. Based on the researchers' findings, the Sub-Coordinator of Budgeting stated that instructors at the center could be sufficient, but they could not be appropriate for the regions themselves. This is indicated by the mismatch between the availability of instructors and vocational training developed by the Ministry of Manpower.

Based on interviews with the Analyst for Material Improvement and Empowerment of Instructors and Training Personnel from the Directorate of Instructor Development and Training Personnel, he said that the existing instructors were inadequate both at the central and regional levels. The implementing in this vocational training is an instructor. Each training center's instructors are civil servants with specific educational criteria each year. However, in recruiting human resources, instructors still have their obstacles, namely teaching abilities. So that new instructors are accepted, requiring basic instructor training. Then in his statement said that it needs improvement for teaching skills or how to deliver material to trainees and carry out a program of upgrading the instructor's skills so that they can adapt to current industrial developments. He stated that there were 3,286 government instructors and 5,807 private instructors. This means that the number mentioned still needs more carrying out vocational training programs that are spread nationally.

The author can conclude that the input aspects of vocational training still have deficiencies, especially in financial, facilities, and human resources. Fluctuating budget allocation means that vocational training has performance achievement problems. Then, training center facilities that have not been spread evenly throughout the country are a different problem. Then, the number and capacity of implementing instructors for the regions need to be improved.

Process (Process Evaluation)

Based on the planning and results of interviews with the functional planners of the Ministry of Manpower, there are three workforce planning units, namely the echelon 2 unit, Ministry of National Development Planning of the Republic of Indonesia, and the internal Planning and Performance Management Bureau. Through this, the Bureau of Planning and Performance Management

accommodates all needs from the results of the studies of the three work units. After the needs have been accommodated, macro program planning emerges that responds to the study's results. Once compiled, then the program planning was implemented.

Based on interviews with the Sub Coordinator for Vocational Training Implementation, the implementation of vocational training is supported through the 2022 Competency Based Training technical manual; the stages of implementation are set out in Regulation of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration Number 8 of 2014, consisting of introduction (introduction/preparation), serving, application, assessment/assessment, determination of graduation, training certificate.

The Sub-Coordinator of Vocational Training Implementation stated that the implementation of vocational training was by procedures. The procedures are carried out according to the applicable policy rules, starting from the President's directives in the form of Presidential Decree number 68 of 2022, the strategic plan of the Ministry of Manpower, to the Decree of the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development Number 2/2887/LP.03.02/XII/2021 concerning Technical Instructions for Training Competency-Based. In his statement, he also emphasized that the procedure for implementing the training had been neatly arranged according to the schedule, starting from recruitment, selection, and implementation, when it was completed, up to the evaluation stage.

One example of the implementation of electrical vocational training is explained as follows; "The assessment of this aspect is intended to measure the effectiveness of teaching and learning activities in training. There are three factors of concern in this aspect: the techniques and teaching strategies of instructors, interactions in teaching and learning activities, and the measurement of trainee competency. The evaluation results show that this aspect tends to be very good even though it does not show significant differences in either category." (Darmawan et al., 2020).

The implementation of the above program is excellent but makes little difference. This means that more than providing vocational training to participants is required. The government's role in spreading the placement of participants after graduation is undoubtedly needed. This is in line with the statement based on an interview with the Sub-Coordinator of Budgeting Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development that placement-oriented training is still needed. In the sense that the institution is not just training it, and then after that, it is finished. Of course, this is inappropriate training because the initial goal of the Ministry of Manpower is to reduce unemployment.

Based on the picture under, there are nine stages in implementing Competency Based Training:

Process at Sisnaker : 1, 5, 6, 7 and 9

Process at LPK: 2, 3, 4 and 8

Process Filling Evaluation/Survey at Sisnaker 5, 6, 7 and 9

Figure 2. Stages of the process of implementing Competency Based Training

Source: Decree of the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development Number 2/2887/LP.03.02/XII/2021

First, The training registration process at the employment information system. The two processes of selection and specialization of training by the institute. Second, the training institute conducted the determination of training participants. Third, Training at training institute offline, online, or blended. Fourth, Fill in the ratings and reviews on the employment information system. Fifth, Evaluate the satisfaction of organizing institute training at employment information systems. Sixth, A survey on work readiness in an employment information system. Seven, Pass the training and get a certificate from the training institute. Eight, Fill out a job survey at the empathy employment information system after graduation in the first month, third month, and sixth month.

The recruitment process for registration of trainees at the Pandeglang Regency Vocational Training Center includes outreach and creating an account at the Ministry of Manpower (Wahyuningsih et al., 2021). Based on this explanation, the recruitment process refers to the regulation of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration Number 8 of 2014. Overall the recruitment and selection process can be described as follows: 1) Disseminate information about the training that will be held and the requirements 2) Register potential participants. 3) Prepare a recapitulation list of potential participants. 4) Determine the selection method to be used by predetermined requirements. Selection can be made by one or a combination of the following methods: Written test., Interview., Recognition of Current Competency (RCC) or recognition of current competencies, Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL), or recognition of previous learning outcomes (formal, non-formal, or work experience). 5) Conduct a selection of potential participants. Purpose of selection: To select potential participants according to the specified requirements; To determine prospective trainees' condition (knowledge, skills). The data/information from the two objectives is used as a basis for starting the training. 6) Set the election results. 7) Announce the results of the selection. 8) Prepare a list of participants who have been declared accepted. 9) Make complete data of training participants.

In more detail, the participant recruitment and selection process chart is illustrated as follows:

Figure 3. Recruitment Process and Selection Of Participants
Source: Minister of Manpower and Transmigration Regulation No. 8 of 2014

The recruitment process begins with a TNA or Training Needs Analysis to identify the needs of the business world, job market, or industry needs. After knowing these needs, the training institute determines the needs by following work competency standards arranged through a training program. This training program creates modules, curricula, and syllabi, which are then used for training programs. After the training program is arranged, proceed to carry out recruitment as in the chart above.

An interview with North Jakarta regional job training center Instructors explained that in the regional job training center, the vocational training process begins with initial recruitment. The initial form of recruitment for training was in the form of mobile marketing to the public in the form of information. Marketing is carried out in collaboration with Sub-Districts, and High Schools

throughout North Jakarta. So, in this case, the training participants are free from any criteria and primarily domiciled in North Jakarta.

After the participants had registered, the North Jakarta regional employment training center selected 20 electrical engineering majors. After that, the participants are trained depending on the initial policy and the job market, whether they want quality or quantity of participants. If we want quality, the training can be up to 45 days. If we want quantity, the training will be 30 days and add two days for competency exams. So far, training has been carried out offline by visiting the training center at the regional employment training center in North Jakarta because electricians need training repetition so that participants can understand and memorize the stages of work. During training in a year, there are usually 3 to 4 batches. It all depends on the industry's needs.

The implementation of the supervision process is carried out by supervising and monitoring the progress of the program's vocational training. Each work unit carries out monitoring to ensure that the implementation of the program is carried out according to the planning carried out. At the same time, supervision is carried out by the Inspectorate General, Audit Board of the Republic of Indonesia, and Internal Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development. In its supervision, there is no good cooperation from each work unit, based on the applicable statement of the planner from the Ministry of Manpower. This means there is no synergy in supervising the implementation of vocational training at the Ministry of Manpower.

Based on an interview with the North Jakarta regional employment training center Instructor, he said that there were still obstacles and inhibiting factors during the training. The inhibiting factor is when participants request training at a higher level while they do the training at the operator level. During the training, there was only one level of training, not the advanced level, that should be trained in vocational training. Then also, the North Jakarta regional employment training center Instructor stated that this training needed to be more flexible with the demands of the job market. When companies want training B, but the regional job training center conducts training A, looking at it from a budget perspective, the budgeting for that year has already been implemented. Therefore, implementation is still constrained by a strict budget determined at the beginning of the year. Of course, with this, it is miserable to miss the opportunity for the government to be able to link and match employment through training and distribute or place training participants.

Performance report of the Directorate General of Vocational Training Development and Productivity for 2021, achievements in 2021, the program is carried out with activities to improve and organize vocational training carried out at 21 central technical implementation units, 250 regional technical implementation units in 33 Provinces, Community, and 34 Provincial Offices throughout Indonesia. The target for achievement in 2021 is 65%, with the realization of training achievements of 233,500 people, placement as of 14 February 2022 of 138,034 people or 59.12%. This means that the planned target of 65% by the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development has yet to be implemented optimally, which can be seen by the performance achievement level of 90.95%.

Table 1. Details of the realization of achievements in 2021

No.	Training	Targets (people)	Realization (person)	Placement (person)
1.	Competency Based Training	120.046	122.119	35.999
2.	Overseas Internship	600	583	583
3.	Domestic Internship	8.300	8.290	4.133
4.	Independent Internship	100.000	12.972	7.783
5.	Independent Workforce	100.000	89.536	89.536
	Amount	328.946	233.500	138.034

Source: Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development performance report for 2021.

Based on the table above, the details of the realization of vocational training in 2021 are explained. In Competency Based Training, there were 122,119 people, and 35,999 people had been placed. The realization of overseas internships was 583 people and also placed 583 people. Domestic internships have realized 8,290 people, with 4,133 placed. Independent internships were realized for

as many as 12,972 people, with placements of 7,783 people. Independent workers realized as many as 89,536 people with a placement of 89,536. This means that the realization of the implementation of vocational training in 2021 has not been achieved from the planned target.

The revised ceiling financial realization data lists indications of needing to be implemented successfully. The Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development in 2021 has a budget allocation of 2,485,438,547.00, and the Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development of 2,412,465,084,506 has realized the budget. With this realization, the absorption of the budget by the Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development has not been optimal, so the process of implementing vocational training programs has not been carried out properly through indications of targets for achievement and realization of the budget.

In the author's opinion, that aspect of the vocational training process must be adequately implemented. Indications not implemented are seen from the implementation of the level of training that is only at the operator—furthermore, the instructor's ability to transfer knowledge to participants. Then, there needs to be synergy in supervising vocational training, which can cause discrepancies in reports. Then, the realization of target achievement and the use of budgets that are not optimal so that vocational training has yet to be carried out correctly.

Product (Product Evaluation)

Based on the Ministry of Manpower's 2017 performance report, vocational training is still called increasing the competence and productivity of the workforce. The percentage of workers with competency certificates has a target of 2.73%. Realization program of 2.67%. In more detail, in 2017, it was realized that 472,089 people had competency certificates. The level of labor productivity in 2017 has a target of 76.30%, with a realization of 81.91%. This means that vocational training in 2017 still has yet to reach the target of planning in competency-certified workforce indicators.

In 2018, the percentage of the workforce with competency certificates had a target of 3.10%. The realization reached 3.10% with details of 615,388 people. The level of labor productivity in 2018 had a target of 77.65 million people, and 84.07 million people were realized. Then in 2019, the target of a certified workforce is 3.5%, with a realization of 3.76%. The details are 911,152 people. At the level of labor productivity, it has a target of 79.1 million people, with a realization of 86.6 million people. This means that vocational training in 2018-2019 has reached the target, but the increase in the number of targets from the previous year was tiny.

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic occurred, which resulted in no vocational training being implemented as it should have been. Based on data from the Ministry of Manpower's 2021 performance report, vocational training in 2020 will change its name to increasing workforce competitiveness with vocational training. Have training and placement performance indicators. The target for training in 2020 is 116,260 people. The realization of 121,049 people and 33,408 people has been placed as of February 2021.

Based on the 2021 Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development report, vocational training has a target of 65% with a realization of 59.12%. Participants who participated in the training were 233,500 people, and 138,034 were placed. Vocational training in 2021 has not been successfully carried out with the realization that it is less than the target. Then, the guaranteed placement of post-training participants is also not all. This means that cooperation with the labor market industry cannot guarantee that the labor market will absorb participants.

Based on an interview with the Reporting Evaluation section of the Secretariat of the Director General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development, it was stated that some vocational training reached the target and some did not. In line with the Reporting Evaluation section, the Sub-Coordinator of Budgeting stated that the implementation of the training would be achieved; the obstacle was monitoring placement. One example of placement constraints is Fadilah and Weni's writings: "In numbers and results of alumni reports to central technical implementation unit Mojokerto that alumni who already have jobs after attending industrial electricity training are around 60% more" (Fadilah & Rosdiana, n.d.)

As many as 40% of trained trainees still do not get a job. In this case, it indicates that the aim of holding vocational training has yet to be successful in finding a link and match of employment to the labor market and reducing unemployment. The performance report of the Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development for 2021, the program's target of increasing competence and competitiveness of the workforce, seen from implementing indicators 1, has yet to reach the set target. So the statement from the Sub-Coordinator of Budgeting needs to be revised. Not only that, the expert level planner I, program evaluation reporting Secretariat Vocational Training and Productivity Development, said the substance of the results was by the duties and functions of the Ministry of Manpower as stated in the strategic plan targets. Therefore, the performance achievements of the

Directorate General of Vocational Training and Productivity Development work targets have yet to be achieved and successfully implemented.

Manpower is a positive one. First, to reduce the unemployment rate, training programs can be an initial capital for human resources in Indonesia to be absorbed into the job market. Furthermore, an interview statement with the Sub-Coordinator of Budgeting said that the impact felt was, of course, from the skills of the people themselves; when they entered the job market, they were already prepared with the skills they had. This skill is manifested through a certificate issued by the national body for professional certification. The vocational training program does not have a direct impact but indirectly by increasing human resource skills. In line with this statement, an example of the impact of graphic design training in Banyuwangi is that participants can be skilled, creative, and professional in creating a design. It is supported as follows: "The success of the trainees includes knowledge, skills, and attitudes." (Dianingtyas et al., 2021, p: 65).

This means that by holding the training, the training participants can have three indirect impacts, namely knowledge, skills, and attitudes. In more detail, the article explains that the training participants are sufficiently provided with knowledge and provisions for opening business opportunities. The knowledge referred to in this case is in the form of skills in graphic design. In terms of skills, the training results through repetition, an iterative process, so the trainees can understand specific patterns and become proficient in skills. This is in line with the statement of the North Jakarta regional job training center Electrical Instructor that in conducting operator training, the trainees need repetition in practice so that the trainees have an understanding and can memorize the patterns repeatedly. In attitude or attitude, change at the will of the trainees. The attitude of wanting to change oneself by participating in training, and being responsible for oneself, can be indicated as the success of the trainees in changing themselves. It is written as follows: "Many of the trainees are willing to apply for jobs, some are waiting for calls for work, some are working in printing." (Dianingtyas et al., 2021 p:65). Furthermore, the quality of vocational training participants are said to be good, the statement is supported as follows: "The quality of the results from the computer training program at training center Bantul is good. Training participants in learning activities have acquired knowledge and skills regarding computer training. This is evidenced by the results achieved after skilled trainees completed the training program in operating computers." (Ernawati & Suyantiningsih, 2020).

The statement above explains the quality of the provision of training to trainees going well. Participants can understand the learning process. Furthermore, participants may have computer knowledge and skills to operate computers. It is indicated that the trainees have skills in computer operation. However, remember that more than improving skills is needed when trained. The article needs to explain whether, after being trained, they can get the right job according to the training they attended. This cannot be said to be successful because there is no placement after the training.

Based on the interview results, the Vocational Training Implementation Sub-Coordinator said two impacts had arisen. The incredible impact of community interest in the training, the interest was very high; out of 10 classes held, each class only accommodated 16 people, but the total enrollment was 900 people, so it can be interpreted that the existence of a vocational training program has a good impact on the level of community interest in participating in the training provided. Then with the destructive impact on the mentality of accepting post-training placements. When they have finished the training and get work placements out of town, the trainees do not want to, and some parents do not allow them to go out of town. Paying attention to this, the government needs to be more mature in implementing the program because it still blames the community when its target cannot be achieved.

Based on an interview with the North Jakarta regional job training center Electrical Instructor stated that there is no guarantee after being trained on the job. This is due to the lack of cooperation between the local government and related companies. The Training Needs Analysis had yet to be carried out properly before the training. So it does not reduce the unemployment rate. In carrying out Training Needs Analysis, of course, seeing the potential in the area will require the necessary expertise; only then can training be carried out. When the training is finished, the participants cannot enter the world of work, meaning that no link and match has been found in employment.

Training Personnel said the impact resulting from the program was still less than the number of training held by the Ministry of Manpower. They looked at the national targets that need to be improved and people in the regions who still need to learn about vocational training at the training center. Through this, the promotion of the implementation of vocational training programs still needs improvement. Furthermore, this program had little impact based on interviews with North Jakarta regional job training center Instructors. The North Jakarta regional job training center instructor stated that the training participants did not need long training

because they also needed income during the training period. This means that this vocational training is still impacted by the trainees' economic conditions.

The impact of evaluating the Ministry of Manpower's vocational training during the COVID-19 pandemic period in 2021 is following the Ministry of Manpower's strategic plan to improve the quality of Indonesian people. Evaluation of vocational training is used to see how the performance of vocational training has been carried out contributes to success or failure. In terms of the impact of the vocational training provided, individual beneficiaries improve their competencies, skills, and attitudes. After improving individual capabilities, it simultaneously contributes to national productivity.

Systematic evaluation of vocational training in this study seeks and explains the impact of vocational training. From the results of the research, it was concluded that the vocational training for the Ministry of Manpower during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021 had not had a real impact when compared to the annual workforce. Let us look at the training realization data before and after the pandemic. The number of workers trained is still in the hundreds of thousands, while the Indonesian workforce is in the hundreds of millions. Furthermore, the trainees have yet to receive a guarantee that they will work after attending the training.

However, according to the author, the positive impact felt by individuals is in the form of increasing self-ability; in preparing themselves for a competitive labor market competition, it is advisable that vocational training should be continued by improving the input, process, and product aspects of vocational training. It was bearing in mind that the tremendous impact felt by individuals can help increase national productivity by improving the quality of the Indonesian workforce.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion on the evaluation of the Ministry of Manpower's vocational training during the COVID-19 pandemic, it is still not successful if carefully analyzed. The context aspect has answered the employment situation during the pandemic. However, input aspects, such as budget, assets, and human resources, have yet to be sufficient during the implementation of vocational training. Then, the implementation process still has obstacles in the form of a small number of training classes, disproportionate budgets, uncoordinated supervision, and the need to upgrade trainers' skills to the employment survey system. Afterward, information about vocational training has yet to reach remote areas. In addition, the implementation product must be specific so that after the participants have finished being given the training, they will be accepted into the world of work or work placements so that it does not impact the training participants.

REFERENCES

1. Avis, J. (2018). Socio-technical imaginary of the fourth industrial revolution and its implications for vocational education and training: a literature review. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 70(3), 337–363. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2018.1498907>
2. BPS. (2020). *Berita Resmi Statistik :Keadaan Ketenagakerjaan Indonesia Agustus 2020*. www.bps.go.id.
3. BPS. (2021). *Keadaan Ketenagakerjaan Indonesia Agustus 2021*. <https://www.bps.go.id/>
4. BPS. (2021). *Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Indonesia Triwulan IV-2020*. www.bps.go.id, 13, 12.
5. Clark, & Cresswell. (2014). *Qualitative Research Designs: Recognizing The Overall Plan For A Study. Exceptional Children*.
6. Cresswell, J., & Cresswell, D. (2018). *Qualitative Methods. Qualitative Inquiry*, 36–47.
7. Creswell, J. W. (2013). Standards of Validation and Evaluation (Perspectives). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design*, 244–255.
8. Daniel L. Stufflebeam, & Coryn, C. L. S. (2014). *Evaluation Theory, Models, and Applications* (Second ed). Jossey-Bass.
9. Darmawan, I. A., Budiyanata, N. E., Aribowo, D., Fatkhurokhman, M., Hamid, M. A., Guntara, Y., & Nurhaji, S. (2020). Electricity course on vocational training centers: A contribution to unemployment management. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1456(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1456/1/012048>
10. Dirjen Binalavotas. (2021). Keputusan Direktur Jenderal Pembinaan Pelatihan Vokasi dan Produktivitas Nomor 2/2887/LP.03.02/XII/2021 Tentang Petunjuk Teknis Penyelenggaraan Pelatihan Berbasis Kompetensi Tahun Anggaran 2022.
11. Dirjen Binalavotas. (2021). *Laporan Kinerja Direktorat Jenderal Pembinaan Pelatihan Vokasi dan Produktivitas*.

12. Ernawati, Y., & Suyantiningsih. (2020). Studi Evaluasi Program Pendidikan dan Pelatihan Komputer di Balai Latihan Kerja Kabupaten Bantul. *Epistema*, 1(1).
13. Fadilah, E. N., & Rosdiana, W. (2015). Evaluasi Pelatihan Insitiusional pada Sub Kejuruan Listrik Industri di Unit Pelaksana Teknis (UPT) Pelatihan Kerja Mojokerto. *Publika*.
14. Istiyani, N. M., & Utsman, U. (2020). Evaluasi Program Model CIPP Pada Pelatihan Menjahit Di LKP Kartika Bawen. *Learning Community: Jurnal Pendidikan Luar Sekolah*, 3(2), 6. <https://doi.org/10.19184/jlc.v3i2.16810>
15. Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan. (2020). Laporan Kinerja Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan Tahun 2020. <https://kemnaker.go.id/>
16. Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan. (2021). *Laporan Kinerja Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan Tahun 2021*. <https://kemnaker.go.id/>
17. Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan. (2021). *Peraturan Menteri Ketenagakerjaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 10 Tahun 2021 Tentang Rencana Strategis Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan Tahun 2020-2024*.
18. Miles, & Huberman. (2014). *Our View of Qualitative Data Analysis*. In *Qualitative Data Analysis* (pp. 24–34). SAGE Publications.
19. Müller, A. (2016). The digital nomad: Buzzword or research category? *Transnational Social Review*, 6(3), 344–348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21931674.2016.1229930>
20. Olga, H. (2020). In search of a digital nomad: defining the phenomenon. *Information Technology and Tourism*, 22(3), 335–353. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40558-020-00177-z>
21. Ridwan, I., & Suryono, Y. (2015). Evaluasi Program Pelatihan Vokasi di Sanggar Kegiatan Belajar Ujung Pandang Kota Makassar. <http://journal.uny.ac.id/index.php/jppm>
22. Saputra, H., & Salma, N. (2020). Dampak PSBB dan PSBB Transisi di DKI Jakarta dalam Pengendalian COVID-19. *Media Kesehatan Masyarakat Indonesia*, 16(3), 282–292. <https://doi.org/10.30597/mkmi.v16i3.11042>
23. Sari, H., Idris, U., & Novalina, A. (2020). Evaluasi Program Pelatihan Berbasis Kompetensi Bagi Calon Tenaga Kerja Di Unit Pelaksanaan Teknis Dinas Balai Latihan Kerja Pengembangan Produktifitas Dan Keterampilan Transmigrasi Dinas Tenaga Kerja dan Transmigrasi Provinsi Sumatera Selatan. *Jurnal Administrasi Publik*, 25(02), 26–41.
24. Setianingrum, A. (2016). *Implementasi Model Evaluasi CIPP Pada Pelaksanaan Program Pendidikan Dan Pelatihan Di BPTT Darman Prasetyo Yogyakarta*. In <https://eprints.uny.ac.id/>. Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.
25. Shah, A. (2020). *Policy, Program and Project Evaluation: A Toolkit for Economic Analysis in a Changing World*.
26. Stufflebeam, D. L., & Coryn, C. L. S. (2014). *Evaluation Theory, Models, And Applications* (Second Edition). Wiley publishes. <http://booksupport.wiley.com>.
27. Wahyuningsih, T., Darmawan, I. A., & Hamid, M. A. (2021). Evaluation of Electrical Installation Training Conducted by the Employment Training Center of Pandeglang Regency, Banten, Indonesia. *JPPM (Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat)*, 8(2), 169–185. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jppm.v8i2.42116>
28. Woodcock, J., & Graham, M. (2020). *The Gig Economy A Critical Introduction*. Cambridge: Polity Press

Cite this Article: Stevanus Agung Wibowo, Tomi Setiawan, Sinta Ningrum (2022). Evaluation of Vocational Training during the COVID-19 Pandemic Period in Indonesia. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 5(12), 4843-4855